

THE PROBLEMS OF MODERN LINGUISTICS AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstarct.

It is a well-known fact that an indispensable condition for the implementation of any communicative act must be a mutual knowledge of realities by the speaker and the listener, which is the basis of language communication. These values have received in linguistics the name of background knowledge. A word reflecting an object or phenomenon of the reality of a particular society not only means it, but also creates some background associated with this word.

Key words.

Foreign language, method, knowledge, skills, translation, problem.

Linguistics as a field of study flourished tremendously beyond the hopes of its founders. Modern linguistics started a cognitive revolution in the 1950s and has been extending ever since. Thanks to linguistics we know so much about human languages than ever before, from their origins, why are there so many of them, and how to use language to solve crimes. Not only that, linguistics gave us pretty compelling insights into the nature of the human mind, how to build talking machines, how to train people with dyslexia so they can read, how to repair brain functions that pertain to language, etc. It is an impressive feat.

At present, the need to learn English in its actual functioning in various spheres of human activity has become generally accepted. In our university, English is taught throughout all the years of study, in all specialties; electrical engineering, programming and management, and the main task of training is the mastery of students' communication skills in English. If we consider the first two specialties, then much attention is paid to teaching students to "communicate" with technology, and managers, in turn, can not do without communication with people. Therefore, in the last year of training, the emphasis is on business English, where the communicative method of instruction is the main one. However, here we are faced with a number of communicative problems of linguistics. The experience of teaching shows that even at advanced stages of training students admit a

significant number of errors both in the performance of exercises and in the use of substantive constructions in conversational practice. Incorrect use of these structures in the composition of a complex sentence leads to a violation of the logic of the utterance and, as a consequence, to nonfulfillment of the tasks of communication. In this regard, we see the need for more detailed equipping of this topic and the development of relevant recommendations. Another obstacle on the way to solving the communicative problem of linguistics is the correct perception of the said form, that is, the perception of what has been said by ear. The next problem is the translation of the form into a common meaning. At this stage, it is important that the listener knows at least one, the most common meaning of the word, which was told to others.

Therefore, when teaching English as a means of communication, it is important to make it clear to students that a person perceives what is said through their individual and cultural prism, and therefore, it is necessary, as accurately as possible, to convey all the meanings that the word carries within itself. The transition from cultural to individual values is manifested in the projection of cultural values through the prism of some of their own properties, attitudes. This is the barrier in communication, which is called psychological, and is the most difficult to overcome in communication between individuals, because for all people the mechanism of "encryption" and "decryption" is different and depends on various reasons, one of which is the different psychology of people. Therefore, the urgency of the communicative problem has now acquired an unprecedented poignancy.

This problem is also connected with one of the problems of the theory of translation, namely with the methods of transfer of the equivalent vocabulary, i.e. vocabulary, which has no analogues in a different culture. It, in turn, creates a great obstacle in communication between people of different cultures. The solution to this problem we see in the expansion of background knowledge of students. Background vocabulary are words or expressions that have additional content and accompanying semantic or stylistic nuances that overlap with its basic meaning, known to the speaker and listener belonging to a given language culture. Therefore, an important stage in teaching communication is to familiarize students with the realities, traditions and customs of English-speaking countries. The use of the linguistic and cultural aspect contributes to the formation of the motivation of the teaching, which is very important in the conditions of studying in the college because foreign language communication is not supported by the language environment. When learning a language, simultaneously with the condition of each

lexeme, the lexical concept associated with it is formed. If the lexeme is acquired and articulated correctly, this does not yet indicate that the lexical concept has been completed. In the educational process, it should be borne in mind that the word is simultaneously a sign of reality and a unit of language. Therefore, nonequivalent and background vocabulary needs comment, requires special attention of the teacher. Equivalent vocabulary is the property of culture. If we compare two national cultures, then we can conclude that they never completely coincide. This follows from the fact that each language consists of national and international elements, and for each culture, the totality of these elements will be different. We introduce students to language units that most clearly reflect the national characteristics of the culture of the native speaker of the language and among its existence. In addition, the content of the national culture also includes the social component, on the basis of which knowledge about the realities and rights of the countries of the studied language, knowledge and skills of communicative behavior in acts of speech communication, skills and abilities of verbal and non-verbal behavior are formed. Due to the fact that students do not have the opportunity to communicate directly with the native speaker of the language being studied, the teacher needs to explain and explain certain characteristics of the culture of native speakers, we often face the problem of students' lack of understanding of the characteristics and culture of the native speaker. In this regard, we are trying to select the language material reflecting the culture of the country of the studied language, the so-called realities. In realities, the closeness between language and culture is most clearly manifested. A distinctive feature of reality from other words of the language is the nature of its subject content, i.e. the close connection of the designated reality of the object or phenomenon with the national, on the one hand, and the historical interval of time-on the other hand. Reality as a linguistic phenomenon is most closely connected with the culture of the country of the studied language, since it has a national and historical color.

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